

The implementation of rice-fish technology in rainfed lowland on production and agricultural business feasibility (Case Study Nglanggeran Agrotechnopark, Gunungkidul, Yogyakarta)

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ABSTRACT

Rice-fish-integrated rice and fish cultivation is an alternative to optimize farmers' income. Farmers in DIY cultivate usually only irrigated rice and limited in rainfed field agro-ecosystem in relation to this, a trial of the location-specific rice-fish technology was conducted. This study aims to determine the income and feasibility of rice-fish business by comparing 3 (three) technology packages: 1) rice-fish, variety of Inpari-30, path-row planting system of 2: 1, recommended fertilizer for soil and catfish, 2) rice -fish, Ciherang variety, path-row planting system of 2: 1, recommended fertilizer for red tilapia, 3) existing pattern (monoculture). This research was carried out in rainfed lowland on March-July 2017 in the Nglanggeran Agro Techno Park area, Patuk Gunungkidul. The results showed that the best rice production was reached in the first package of rice-fish with Inpari 30 productivity of 7.85 t/ha harvest dry, followed by the second package with Ciherang productivity of 6.98 and package 3 (the existing pattern) of 5.92 t/ha harvest dry. Based on the net income of rice technology, package 1 and 2 was IDR 32,272,400 and IDR 30,957,400 compared to the existing pattern of equal to IDR 11.589.000. Based on the financial analysis showed that technology packages 1 and 2 were feasible with a ratio of $RC > 1.0$ (2.17 and 2.10, respectively) with an increase in income between 60.35 – 64.09 percent compared to the monoculture pattern. It was concluded that the rice-fishrice-fish model with the enlargement pattern of catfish and red tilapia package 1 and 2 is feasible to be developed in rainfed lowland in Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta and can be used as an alternative income optimization

Keywords: *Rice-fish new rice varieties, rainfed lowland, yield, feasibility*

INTRODUCTION

The integrated fish and rice cultivation model is an alternative technology to solves problems in increasing income and maintaining rice productivity in the rice fields. The principle of rice-fish patternutilizes rice fields when puddles are long enough to be used for fish rearing without reducing the total grain harvested later. The rice-fish can be applied when the water is

available and excessive and has good quality for fish to grow (Widodo et al., 2014).

The implementation of rice-fish technology is still limited in in the field, but is growing quite rapidly in Sleman Regency, DIY. Rice-fish is location-specific depending on the problems that will be addressed (demand driven technologies). According to Widodo et al., (2015), rice crop management with rice-fish cultivation system is an innovative approach in efforts to increase productivity and efficiency in the cost of rice plants, because it is more economical in the use of rice production costs (production, energy), but expensive in the provision of fish and costs feed. According to Ardiwinata (1987), rice-fishrice-fish was developed a century ago, but now has long been abandoned. Instead the rice-fish model is growing rapidly in Sleman Regency, Yogyakarta (Department of Agriculture and Food, Regency of Sleman, 2017).

According to Suriapermana (1994),rice-fish is one of the efforts to optimize technical irrigated rice fields with appropriate engineering technology specific locations in rice fields. According to Tupan et al., (2013), another benefit in the rice-fish pattern in paddy fields is to increase soil fertility, reduce pests and diseases in rice plants. Many technologies that have been tested on agricultural land to improve the quality of the environment in anticipating climate anomalies, the good technology is integrated rice-fish. Rice-fish has been developed in Indonesia since a century ago. Rice-fish partly contributes to reducing emissions of methane gas (CH₄) and fertilizing the land from fish dung which helps accelerate environmental improvement (Director General of Aquaculture, 2014).

Rice-fish farming can be functioned as follows: (1) as an converser between two rice growing seasons, or together or fish cultivation with rice, and (2) as a substitute for crops in rice fields (Director General of Aquaculture, 2014) The types of fish used for the appropriate oil and gas business are red tilapia, gold fish, grey tilapia, and carp, and some also with carp and catfish (Department Marine and Fisheries Of Yogyakarta. 2014, 2015; Widodo et al., 2015). These types of fish can grow well even in shallow water and are more resistant to sunlight. Rice-fish uses tilapia in rice fields and increasing rice production by 17.05% (30.245 kg/plot), as well as an increase in soil fertility due to the addition of nutrients derived from fish feed and feces containing basic elements of N, P, Ca and Mg (Kaimuddin et al., 2008). This is supported by the results of Fagi et al., (1992), with the rice-fish model and azolla in a stretch can increase soil fertility, control rice weeds and pests and increase rice yield.

The Rice-fish model has a direct impact on the chemical and physical conditions of the land, thus increasing productivity of agricultural land, and reducing the attack of pests and diseases of rice plants. In the biological aspect, the presence of fish will suppress the development of rice plant pests including

golden snails, leafhoppers, stem borer, fish cyclically eat eggs and plant pest larvae whose growth phase is in water. In terms of economics, the Rice-fishbusiness provides multiple benefits, namely from the yields of rice and fish. According to Syamsiah et al., (1988), with rice-fishin addition to providing carbohydrate food, it also provides good protein to improve food quality for rural residents.

Rice-fish business problems in Yogyakarta are limited in capital and technology. Limited land and ownership of irrigated rice fields in Yogyakarta, the best way is to optimize the land by utilizing the land as optimal as possible for business that provide benefits. If only relying on rice yields with narrow land, the income obtained is limited and difficult to meet the standard of living of farmers. Efforts to increase this income are encouraging Yogyakarta farmers to apply rice-fish model. Since 2014 there are 507 fish farmer groups in Sleman Regency (www.sleman.go.id). Based on 2013 data, fish consumption reached 25,883 tons and 947 million fish seeds (Department Marine and Fisheries Of Yogyakarta. 2014).

Based on a research conducted by the Directorate General of Aquaculture in 2011, integrated rice-fish can increase farmers' income in the form of production increase of 10 percent, increase the diversity of agricultural products in the form of fish, increase soil and water fertility, saving fertilizer requirement of 30%, and reduce pests of leafhopper and brown planters on rice plants (Widodo et al., 2014; Widodo, 2017). Rice-fish is considered as one of the solutions in dealing with the low productivity due to extreme weather. The Rice-fish model enriches the growing media with organic fertilizer and increases the production of plankton as a source of fish food, and contribute fish to this integrated farming business (Simanjuntak 2013). According to Montazeri 2012 in Kustiari et al., (2016), rice-fish model is one of the agricultural land technologies to improve the environmental quality in anticipating climate anomalies

According to the experience of Mr. Timbul in Sleman District, rice-fish gives a double profit of grain and red tilapia between IDR 2,500,000, - up to 3,050,000 per 1,000 m² (personal interviews in 2016 and 2017). The results of Rahma (2008) who compares between rice-fish and monoculture showed that the rice-fish pattern gave higher acceptance than the monoculture pattern, namely 1) the total revenue of rice-fish farming combined by two commodities namely rice and fish amounting to IDR 9,835,779.80 per hawhile the monoculture pattern is IDR 7,941,238.13 per ha. It was also said that the income function of rice-fish such as the variable amount of rice production, rice production costs and fish production costs had a significant effect on the income of rice-fish. Based on the potential of extensive rainfed rice fields in the Agrotechnopark region and the availability of sufficient water from the results of groundwater drilling and several natural spring sources in the Purba Volcano

area, the application of rice-fish can be carried out so as to provide added value to farmers in Agrotechnopark area, Gunungkidul Regency is overweight. With utilizing some technologies such as high yielding variety, path-row planting system, site-specific fertilization and water pumping, the rice-fish system can be pioneered to be developed in dry land/rainfed rice fields. This study aims to determine the income and feasibility of rice mina technology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in rainfed rice fields, Nglanggeran Agrotechnopark area, Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta province in March - July 2017. The study compared 3 (three) technology packages, namely two rice-fish technological packages and 1 existing technological package. Both rice-fish technology packages was applied in each with an area of 1,500 m², while the IR 64 variety was an existing pattern with an average area of 1,500 m² (covers 4 farmers). Rice-fish pattern used path-row planting system of 2: 1 (spacing of 25 cm x 12.5 cm x 50 cm). Fertilizer dosage was based on recommendation from soil nutrients analysis, namely 200 kg urea, 250 kg phonska, 50 kg KCl, and 3.0 tons manure per ha. The manure was applied once three days before planting, while urea was split 3 times, phonska and KCl twice with a dose of ½ dose. Urea fertilizer was applied at 7 days after planting, 21 days after planting and 35 days after planting, while phonska and KCl were applied at 7 days after planting and 21 after planting.

Fish used for assessment are catfish and red tilapia specifically for enlargement patterns, with 5-7 cm stocking size. The 2: 1 planting system was used for rice-fish technology packages which combined with shallow trenches and a center with a width of 0.80 m. Grinding of water for rice-fish is adjusted to the age of the plant. In this study the enlargement of fish was maintained until harvesting time of rice plants (70 days). Details in the layout are presented in Table 1.

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Table 1. The rice mina technology package is applied

Component	Technology package Rice mina A	Technology package Rice mina B	Farmers (Eksisting)
Varieties	Inpari 30	Ciherang	IR 64
Seedling age	16-17 days	16-17 days	21 days
Number of seed per hole	1-2	1-2	3-5
Manure	3,0 t/ha	3,0 t/ha	1 t/ha
Urea	200 kg/ha	200 kg/ha	300 kg/ha
Phonska	250 kg/ha	250 kg/ha	275 kg/ha
KCl	50 kg/ha	50 kg/ha	-
CaCo3 (calsite)	300 kg/ha	300 kg/ha	-
Cropping system	Jarwo 2: 1, inserted, spacing 25x12,5x50 cm; every 20 rows of plants in rows of plants 21 and 22 plants are removed to ditch 0.8 m	Jarwo 2: 1, inserted, spacing 25x12,5x50 cm; every 20 rows of plants in rows of plants 21 and 22 plants are removed to ditch 0.8 m	Tegel 20 x 20 cm
Pattern	Rice mina	Rice mina	Monoculture
Fertilization	3x	3x	2x
Fish type	Lele sp	Red Nila sp	-
Irrigation	Regulated inundation 12 days after planting	Regulated inundation 12 days after planting	Farmer practices
Use of pesticides	limited	limited	Farmer practices
Harvest fish	Maintenance of fish for 70 days until the age of rice harvest	Maintenance of fish for 75 days until the age of rice harvest	-
Types of fish and spreads	Lele sp 20 kg 5-7 cm size; 130 tail/kg	Red Nila sp 28 kg, 7 cm size) ; 120 tail/kg	-
Water resources	shallow well wit pomp, rain water	shallow well wit pomp, rain water	Rain water

The variables observed were (1) the yield of harvested unhulled rice per plot weighed in gray (2.5 m x 2.5 m) as many as 10 samples per plot, then converted to hectares; (2) The age of the plant that calculated from the spread of seeds until harvesting time, (3) the results of the fish harvested until enlargement for 70 days begins to spread the fish after 30 days old rice plant growth.

The data collected included: rice yield components which were traditionally converted into hectares, consumption fish production (4-5 tails/kg red tilapia; 6-7 tails/kg catfish), farming costs (land, labor, production facilities), acceptance, profit, and equipped with a feasibility analysis of the technology applied by comparing the existing monoculture pattern. The analysis details used are as follows:

1. Income

$$I = y \times p \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where: y = production; p = price

2. Production Cost Analysis

Production costs can be calculated by the formula:

$$\text{Total Cost (TC)} = \text{Fixed Cost (TFC)} + \text{Variable Cost (TVC)} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where:

TC = Total Cost; TFC = Total Fixed Cost (fixed costs); TVC = Total Variable Cost (variable cost)

3. Income Analysis

$$TR = Py. Y \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where:

TR = Total Revenue (IDR)

Py = Price of Rice or fish (IDR/kg)

Y = Production of rice and or fish (IDR/kg)

NR = Net Income (IDR/kg)

4. Net income

$$NR = TR - Tceks \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where:

NR = Net Income (IDR/kg)

TR = Total Revenue (Rp)

TCeks = Total Real Costs Issued (Rp)

5. Profit Approach

$$\pi = TR - (TC \text{ explicit} + TC \text{ implicit}) \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Where:

π = Profit (Profit); TR = Total Revenue (Total Revenue); TC = Total Cost (Total Cost)

6. Farming Feasibility Analysis

$$R / C \text{ ratio} = TR / TC \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

Where:

TR = Total gross income; TC = Total Cost

7. Revenue Cost ratio (R / C)

R / C Ratio =

Description of the analysis formula for Revenue Cost Ratio or R / C Ratio above:

R: Total acceptance of the rice-fish business

C: Total production costs of rice-fish business

Criteria information from the Revenue Cost Ratio analysis formula as follows:

a) $R / C \text{ Ratio} > 1$, meaning that the effort is feasible

b) $R / C \text{ Ratio} < 1$, means that the effort is not feasible

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Location and Characterization

Based on the geographical area and location, the study is located at coordinates $7^{\circ} 50'26.052'' \text{ S}$ and $110^{\circ} 32'41.964'' \text{ E}$ with altitude about 400 m above sea level. The average of air temperature is $23.2\text{-}27.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and humidity is 79-89 %, rainfall of 3,400.60 mm/year, 210 days in rainy season per year, and including climate type CB rather wet, location map is presented in Figure 1.

The study area is dominated by rainfed rice fields. The general cropping pattern is rice-rice-secondary crops or fallow. The dominant rice varieties are Ciherang and IR 64 and some local varieties. The majority of jobs are farmers, owners and cultivators and gardening with cocoa cultivation. Productivity of rainfed lowland rice ranges 4.00 to 5.90 t/ha. Most farmers utilize rainfed lowland for planting in WS and second cropping season with additional water supply from the spring source from "Purba" Volcano and drilling groundwater with depths between 20 to 50 m. Field observations for every single point of groundwater drilling can be used to irrigate about 5.00 ha of land, this is especially used in 2nd cropping season, namely March to July with a bi-weekly rotation system. In this case study for an area of about 10.00 ha, a plot of rainfed rice fields, in addition to utilizing rain, pump wells also utilize springs even though with a small discharge but able to meet the needs of rice plants in 2nd cropping season.

Rice varieties are one of the technological components that contribute greatly in increasing productivity and income of rice farming and dry land agro-ecosystem. Other technology components are the management and maintenance of good crop cultivation (cropping systems, balanced fertilization) that will provide normal plant growth and development so that produces optimal production according to expectations. Rice-fishtechnology also apply some components of integrated crop management, namely using young seedlings, planting 1-2 seeds per hole and combined with a 2: 1 path-row planting system which is inserted so that the number of plants is 256,000 hills/ha. With the path-row planting system, a maximum radiation is obtained for plant growth, the row of plants is morelooses for the movement of fish so that the growth of fish is maximal.

Rice Crop Performance

Based on the age of harvest, the result of the operation of the rice-fishbusiness and monoculture rice farming is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Harvesting age, grain yield based dry harvest the area Agricultural Technology Park at Nglanggeran Gunungkidul, Yogyakarta, 2nd cropping season of 2017

Models	Technology Package	Harvest (days)	Grains Yield (t/ha)
Rice-fish	A (Inpari-30)	122	7.85
Rice-fish	B (Ciherang)	117	6.98
Monoculture	C (existing/ IR 64)	117	5.92

Source: Analysis of primary data (2017)

In Table 2, model of rice-fish with Inpari 30 variety yields 7.85 t/ha based dry harvest that higher than rice-fish with Ciherang variety (6.98 t/ha) and the existing pattern using the IR 64 variety (5.92 t/ha). This difference means Inpari 30 has more adaptive and has the ability to stagnate for a long time and provides better yield potential compared to Ciherang and IR 64 varieties. This is in line with the results of Widodo's research (2017) in the development of rice-fish with path-row planting system in irrigated rice fields, the productivity of Inpari 30 (Ciherang Sub-1) was 8.60 tons ha based dry harvest, while the existing variety (IR 64) only produced 5.95 t/ha. This means that rice-fish pattern rice productivity in rainfed lowland is not much different from irrigated rice fields, with the prerequisites for applied technology packages in accordance with the accuracy of planting time, fertilizer dosage and 2:1 path-row planting system. In addition to the reference that the development of the rice-fish model in the rainfed lowland was carried out on site-specific conditions from the

engineering technology supported by the presence of water supplies from bore wells/other spring sources. What should be noted is the striking difference between rice-fish in irrigated rice fields and rainfed lowland is the capacity/spread of fish. For the spread of fish, rice can be denser than rainfed rice fields.

Based on the fertilizer used by rice-fish and monoculture rice, the use in the technology package is slightly lower in dosage. Chemical fertilizer business in rice-fish is given 2/3 s of recommended dose for dry land in Gunungkidul Regency (Department Agriculture and Food of Gunungkidul, 2016). Decreasing chemical fertilizers use for rice-fish technology packages has still yielded grains of 6.00 tons/ha shows that the use of manure and fish waste residue as a supply of organic material is quite good for efficiency in the use of chemical fertilizers. The rice-fish model of the utilization of organic material from manure is absolutely necessary, in addition to functioning as an improvement in soil physical and chemical properties, the use of organic materials also optimizes soil nutrient uptake for plants. Another benefit is the use of manure in the rice-fish pattern as a natural food source because it is able to provide fish feed from the growth of plankton which is a natural food for fish. The results of the research by Rustati and Abdurachman (2011), by optimizing the correct dosage and method of fertilization giving the grain yield and Inpari 30 can still be improved. Increased grain production can be done by applying some components of integrated crop management, namely the use of young seeds and seeds planted by 1 seed per hole.

Simarmata 2006 reported that the more number of seeds planted per hole and the less number of unproductive tillers would be more number of productive tillers, because there was no competition among tillers in the supply of nutrients, This is confirmed by Suriapermana and Syamsiah (1995) that the rice-fish model provides a double advantage of increasing rice production and increasing fish income and saving labor costs for land processing, weeding plants and reducing the cost of chemical fertilizers and pesticides. This results are in line with the results of Sudiarta et al., (2016), that rice-fish model with 2: 1 path-row planting system gave best plant height at 60 days after transplanting, panicle length, panicle weight, grains weight, and addition of fish as well as feasible with R/C and B/C ratio > 1.0. This rice-fish was strengthened by the results of the research by Widodo (2017) that rice-fish model in irrigated rice fields using Inpari-30 can yield 8.0-8.90 t/ha based dry harvest and also provided a profit of IDR 35,845,000.- per ha with a R/C ratio of 2.40.

Cost, Acceptance, Profit and Financial Feasibility

Costs incurred in farming consist of land rent, labor and production facilities. In this analysis all cost factors are considered (explicit costs) to test the feasibility of the business carried out. Business cost component of rice-fish is different from the existing/monoculture pattern. The addition of technology package costs to the components cover water pump and its supporters, fish seeds, fish feed, plastic, trenches, plastic mulch, fuel and others. Based on the production input cost per hectare, the technology package on the A and B banks (land, labor and production facilities) is IDR 27,608,600- and IDR 28,019,400 while the existing/monoculture production costs are lower than IDR 11,795,000 per ha (Table 3).

Revenue is gross income before deducting costs, the results of the application of the rice-fish technology package with Inpari-30 variety after being reduced by a 20% reduction in land area from the use of rice-fish technology for fish enlargement resulted revenue from grain of IDR 24,806,000 per ha. This is in line with the results of Widodo (2017) that application of rice-fish 2: 1 path-row system reduces harvest area by an average of 20% that used for making trenches around the land, and between rows of plants for fish movement. While the fish yield with the technology package on the revenue of catfish is IDR 35,075,000 with fish production of 1,525 kg with a selling price per kg of IDR 23,000. Based on rice-fish technology which is stated in first package, the total income of grain and fish is IDR 59,881,000 per ha. While the rice-fish technology in 2nd package which uses Ciherang and red tilapia varieties can result, revenue from grain sales of IDR 22,056,800 per ha and red tilapia IDR 36,920,000 per ha resulting in total income of IDR 58,976,800 per ha. Detailed analysis is presented in Table 3.

The acceptance of technology package A is more than 1.51% greater than that of technology package B. The revenue component of fish is greater than the revenue from rice harvest. Based on data analysis, the acceptance of fish and grain products by applying the technology on the package A and B ranges 29.28-40.26% which is higher than the fish receipt compared to the income from grain. While the total technology revenue in the US was 60.35 - 64.09%, that higher than the existing technology package/monoculture. From the revenue obtained, the rice-fish technology package is higher than the existing/monoculture pattern. There is a greater income from fish in the rice-fish model. This is in line with the research of Feri-Arlius and Ekaputra (2011) that SRI system can increase rice production from 4.86 t/ha in the conventional practices to 7.80 t/ha with the SRI system and an increase in total income by 46% compared to conventional systems.

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Table 3. Results of financial analysis and business feasibility of rice-fish model in Nglanggeran Agrotechnopark, Gunungkidul, Yogyakarta. March-July 2017 (in 10,000 m)

	ITEMS	Rice mina technology		Existing
		A	B	C
A	Fix cot	3,625.000	3.625.000	3.000.000
	Land rent of 1 ha/year @ ID 6,000,000/2 MT, water pump, etc	3,000,000	3,000,000	3,000,000
B	Labor costs	9.300.000	9.300.000	6.150.000
	Preparation of land until ready for planting, seedling	2,850,000	2.850.000	1,850,000
	Planting and making caren beds, embroidery	2,000,000	2,000,000	425,000
	Weeding and cleaning waled	1.500.000	1.500.000	1.950.000
	Harvesting fish and rice and processing	1,750,000	1,750,000	1,250,000
	Watering and controlling well/drill/source water	625,000	625,000	
	Plastic installation and compaction	250,000	250,000	
C	Variable cost			
	Rice seeds, manure 100 zak	1.000.000	1.000.000	725.000
	Urea, phonska dan KCl fertilizer	1,475,000	1,475,000	1,600,000
	Nila sp fish 200 kg @ IDR 28.000		5,600,000	0
	Lele sp fish 200kg @ IDR 24.000	4,800,000	0	0
	Pelet 14,80 zak (Lele sp), 15,80 zak (Nila)	4,503,600	4,114,400	0
	Probiotik, calcite and pesticide	750.000	750.000	320.000
	Plastic 10 roll (economis 2 year old) oil 120 lt	2.155.000	2.155.000	0
D	Total Cost (A+B+C)	27,608,600	28,019,400	11,795,000
E	Income			
	1. Consumption Nila fish 1.420 kg @ IDR 26.000		36,920,000	0,00
	2. Consumption Lele fish 1.525 kg @ IDR 23.000	35,075,000		
	3. Inpari-30 7.85 t GKP @ 3.950,(CV 20%)	24,806,000		0,00
	4. Ciherang 6,98 t GKP @ 3950, (CV 20%)		22,056,800	
	5. IR 64 5,92 t GKP @ 3.950			23,384,000
	Total Income	59,881,000	58,976,800	23,384,000
	Profit (Tot E - Tot D)	32,272,400	30,957,400	11,589,000
	RC ratio (Tot Incomes/Tot Cost)	2.17	2.10	1.98
	% Increase in receipt of Package A against Existing	60.95	60.35	0
	% Increased receipt of package B to existing	64.09	62.56	0
	% acceptance of fish compared to grain	29.28	40.26	

Source: Analysis of primary data (2017)

Based on profit (net income), a reduction between the total revenue and total costs, the net technology gain of both A and B per hectare was IDR 32,272,400 and IDR 30,057,400, respectively - much higher than the package C (pattern monoculture) which is IDR 11,589,000 per ha. This is due to net income from fish in the rice-fish pattern. The added value of technology fish income on the A and B that compared to the monoculture pattern per hectare is IDR 35,075,000. If including fish component cost with amount of IDR 12,833,600 (catfish) and IDR 13,244,400 (red tilapia), there will be only IDR 22,241,400 and IDR 23,675,600 in net income from fish, or there will be an increase in income from fish of 31.08% and 23.52%, respectively.

The acceptance of technology package A is more than 1.51% greater than that of technology package B. The revenue component of fish is greater than the revenue from rice harvest. Based on data analysis, the acceptance of fish and grain products by applying the technology on the package A and B ranges 29.28-40.26% which is higher than the fish receipt compared to the income from grain. While the total technology revenue in the US was 60.35 - 64.09%, that higher than the existing technology package/monoculture. From the revenue obtained, the rice-fish technology package is higher than the existential/monoculture pattern. There is a greater income from fish in the rice-fish model. This is in line with the research of Feri-Arlius and Ekaputra (2011) that SRI system can increase rice production from 4.86 t/ha in the conventional practices to 7.80 t/ha with the SRI system and an increase in total income by 46% compared to conventional systems.

Based on profit (net income), a reduction between the total revenue and total costs, the net technology gain of both A and B per hectare was IDR 32,272,400 and IDR 30,057,400, respectively - much higher than the package C (pattern monoculture) which is IDR 11,589,000 per ha. This is due to net income from fish in the rice-fish pattern. The added value of technology fish income on the A and B that compared to the monoculture pattern per hectare is IDR 35,075,000. If including fish component cost with amount of IDR 12,833,600 (catfish) and IDR 13,244,400 (red tilapia), there will be only IDR 22,241,400 and IDR 23,675,600 in net income from fish, or there will be an increase in income from fish of 31.08% and 23.52%, respectively.

Based on the feasibility of the business with the approach value ratio revenue cost (RC), the three patterns tested in all feasible with the indicator value ratio revenue cost are above 1.0 (Gittinger, 1986), namely for package of A, B and C patterns with values of R/C ratio of 2.17; 2.10 and 1.98, respectively. Package A is the highest feasibility value that consists of rice-fish with Inpari-30 variety and catfish. Although in terms of business feasibility the monoculture system is feasible, but in terms of low net income, IDR 11,589,000 per ha is much lower than the rice-fish technology pattern system with net income between IDR

30,957,400 - up to IDR 32,272,400; so that it can be recommended that rice-fish technology can be developed in the Agro Techno Park Nglanggeran Gunungkidul area.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The grains yields of application of rice-fish technology in rainfed lowland rice fields at the Agro Techno Park Nglanggeran Gunungkidul area were 7.85 tons/ha for Inpari 30 and 6.98 tons/ha for Ciherang, respectively and higher than the existing pattern (monoculture) with IR 64 (5.92 tons/ha)
2. Net income from farming with technology in the A and B patterns were IDR 32,272,400 and IDR 30,957,400, while the monoculture net income was IDR 11,589,000.
3. The financial feasibility side of the third business package were feasible technology with indicator value ratio revenue cost > 1.0; the highest value of feasibility on rice-fish technology using Inpari-30 variety and catfish scouring system was the value of R/C ratio of 2.17.
4. Considering grain production, total revenue, net income and RC value, the rice-fish technology can be developed on 2nd planting season in rainfed rice fields with additional water from pumping.

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